

The Women's Emotional Language, A Case Study on The Mamesh Squad Socialite Community in Jember City: A Psycholinguistic Study

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Abstract:- The objectives of this study were 1) to identify the diction of the emotional language used by the Mamesh Squad socialite woman who has a SiSeSa branded shirt in Jember City; 2) To identify the emotional language style used by the Mamesh Squad socialite woman who owns the SiSeSa branded clothes in Jember City. The approach used in this research is qualitative. The results showed that first, the diction of emotional language uttered by the Mamesh Squad socialite woman in expressing feelings when having a SiSeSa branded shirt in Jember was found, including abstract words, concrete words, general words, special words, popular words, study words, nonbaku words original words, and loan words as well as denotative and connotative words. The emotional language style used by the Mamesh Squad socialite woman in expressing feelings when having a SiSeSa branded shirt in Jember City consists of four types of language styles contained in the emotions of the Mamesh Squad Socialite woman. Women's emotional expression of all feelings through word selection or diction so as to produce emotional sentences and language styles that can evoke a woman's psychological condition.

Keywords:- language diction, language style, socialite.

I. INTRODUCTION

Language has certain functions in the association between fellow members according to the group (Aslinda and Syafyahya, 2007: 2). In social life, each group has a certain language which is a symbol of its group identity, which is marked by the peculiarities of behavior and language use. This peculiarity is only understood by group members in activities carried out together. Language is the only property of humans that is never separated from all human activities and movements throughout human existence, as cultured and social creatures (Chaer, 2003: 53). There is no human activity that is not accompanied by language, because of the attachment and linkage of language to humans. All human activities are always accompanied by language, because of the attachment and relationship of language to humans.

Emotional language is a language that originates from the dominance of the emotional mind which gives birth to a very strong and overwhelming language (Goleman, 1997:414). Emotion is basically a form of communication. When someone uses language in an emotional state, it means he is conveying a message to another person. One needs to use emotions when speaking in order to bring out the human side.

Emotion is seen as a fundamental social process. The emotional expression of speakers is strongly influenced by social conditions and gender. Forms of emotional expression related to gender can be seen in the effects of gender in emotional expression, physiological responses, and emotional concepts. This explains that gender differences also distinguish emotional expressions (Fisher, 2010: 2). Dardjowidjojo (2003:7) explains that emotions come first through action (body) and through (mind) then take an action. Every human being has thoughts and feelings and emotions. Emotions can be expressions of affection, joy, anger, and hatred. Emotions can stimulate new thoughts, new fantasies, and new behaviors, meaning that emotions can influence a person's behaviour.

Positive emotions or pleasant emotions are emotions that cause positive feelings in the affected people, such as love, affection, joy, admiration and so on. For example, a housewife who has never seen a bear, she may cry out of fear, when he suddenly found a bear in his yard. However, bear trainers will react calmly, not afraid at all because they are used to hanging out with animals (Sarwono, 2009: 130).

Emotional language can be seen from diction, language style, and language patterns. The limited vocabulary that a person has in everyday life can make it difficult for someone to express his meaning to others. Therefore, so that this does not happen, one must know and understand how to use words in communication. One that must be mastered is diction or word choice. Keraf (2007:24) argues that "diction or word choice includes understanding which words are used to convey an idea, how to form the right groupings of words or use the right expressions, and which style is best used in the context of writing, a situation

This research is a case study of socialite women in Jember Regency. Many socialite women's community groups have sprung up in Jember Regency. One of the socialite women's groups in Jember Regency is the Mamesh Squad which is formed from a group of young mothers who are at the Al Furqon school in Jember. The reason for choosing the object in this case study is because the socialite women of the Mamesh Squad are women belonging to the community group with middle to upper economic ability and they have regular activities every month, either social gathering, social service or events from members. Active groups often carry out social activities and are often documented on each member's social media

Female members of the Mamesh Squad generally have professions as entrepreneurs or business owners, whether culinary, fashion, or professionals such as doctors, lecturers and others. The existence of wide association and relationships makes Mamesh Squad members have to maintain an appearance that always follows fashion trends and clothing modes used during routine events or certain events. There are several things that became the basis for considering the selection of the Mamesh Squad socialite woman community as the object of research, namely 1) the use of diction by the Mamesh Squad socialite community; 2) the emotional style used as a marker of the identity of the Mamesh Squad socialite woman.

The reasons for this research were, among others, first, The use of language in expressing the emotion of joy can be categorized as an expression of something new, in this case a new item in the form of SiSeSa clothes. Mastery of language is part of human learning in general, closely related to personality, closely intertwined with the culture of language learning. Second, it involves interference, the creation of new linguistic systems, and the learning of discourse and the communicative function of language (Brown, 1993:151). Joy is an expression of relief, that is, avoiding tension. Usually joy is caused by sudden things and is also usually social, involving other people who are around happy people (Sarwono, 2009: 135). For example, women who recently bought expensive and branded goods.

The aims of study are 1) to identify the emotional language diction used Mamesh Squad socialite women have SiSeSa branded clothes in Jember City and to identify the emotional language style used Mamesh Squad socialite woman owns SiSeSa branded clothes in Jember City.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several studies that have been done before. Mitra Istiar Wardhana (2010) conducted a study entitled *Emotional Expression In Three Face Model Dimensions And Using Bayes Naive Fuzzy Logic*. This research was conducted to identify emotions from Indonesian texts. Text classification is recognized by the various types of emotions that exist in the text using Taner Danisman and Adil Alpkocak identified as basic emotions such as happy, sad, angry, afraid, and disgusted so that the text emotion category was found.

Watuna (2014) conducted a study entitled *"The Use of Language in Expressing Joyful Emotions in the Twilight Saga Film By Stephenie Meyer*. The results of this study indicate that there are several expressions that can be found in expressing feelings of happiness followed by posture and movement support. Marada (2015) conducted a study entitled *"Speech and Body Movements in Expressing Anger in The Hunger Games Trilogy by Suzanne Collins A Psycholinguistic Analysis*. The results of the study explain 58 utterances and body movements in the expression of anger in the film *The Hunger Games Trilogy*, namely: *The Hunger Games, Catching Fire, and Mockingjay*. The expression of anger is expressed by the words *son of bitch, are u crazy?, don't lie/you're lie, get off of me, jerk, are you crazy?, don't*

lie/you're a liar, and the gestures used in an angry state by hitting with hands and feet, pushing, pulling, banging on the door, pointing with the index finger, pointing a gun, pointing a knife, and hitting the table Nurhayati, Hasyim and Muhidin (2018) conducted a study with the title *"Language of Women's Emotions Career in Makassar City (Psychosociolinguistic Studies)*. The results of the study explained that there were nine types of emotions used, including angry, sad, happy, annoyed, afraid, disappointed, complimented, worried, assertive, satisfied, cynical and happy. It colors the lives of career women in carrying out their profession.

A. Language

Language is a system of arbitrary verbal symbols used by the community in communicating and socially interacting with each other based on their own culture (Dardjowidjojo, 2003:16).

The role of language is proven in expressing aesthetic, symbolic, sadness and pleasure in social interactions. In this they express feelings and not thoughts. Therefore, language has a social role, besides the emotional role is to express an idea. Brown (2002: 5) states that language is an arbitrary conventional vocal system, written symbol, or gesture that allows members of a particular community to communicate intelligently with one another.

B. Language Variations

Varieties in language, it is related to the user and its function is called a variety or register function. This variation is based on the use of style or formality and suggestions for using it.

Language variation is a type of language variety that is adapted to functions and situations without producing basic rules in the language concerned. Language variations related to users, users and functions are called *olec-variety functions* or registers. Language variations are usually based on the field of use of style and level of formality with the means of use (Nababan through Chaer, 1995: 89-90).

C. Diction (Word Choice)

Diction is the choice of words in determining a sentence to be good and correct to convey certain aims and objectives. Suheni (2009:52) explains that diction is the choice of words that are appropriate and in harmony (in their use) to explain ideas so that they have an impact. Putrayasa (2007:7) explains that the choice of words comes from the word *dictio* (English in the form of the basic word *dictio*) regarding the choice of words or diction for a sentence. Diction is an essay made up with sentences for the reader to understand.

Based on the understanding, it can be concluded that diction is a person's ability to choose the right and harmonious words to express ideas. This is so that the idea has a certain effect as expected. The choice of words questions the accuracy of the use of words, but also the effect it has on the reader

D. Language style

The style of language used is a way of using language that describes feelings and thoughts that are different from everyday language patterns and are subjective.

Toraf (2010:112) shows that style is the use of the wealth of one's language in speaking or writing; the use of a certain variety in obtaining certain effects, the overall characteristics of the language of a group of literary writers: a distinctive way of thinking and feelings in writing or verbally.

Language style is everything that gives a characteristic to the text, making the text a kind of individual when compared to other texts. Language style is a form of rhetoric, namely the use of words in speaking or writing to convince listeners (Tarigan, 2005:5). Therefore, language style is very important in conveying ideas.

Problem styles included (1) the problem of media in the form of words and sentences, (2) the problem of the relationship of style both with the content of meaning and nuances of its beauty, and (3) the intricacies of the author's own expression which will be closely related to the individual problems of the authorship and the social context of the community behind it (Aminuddin, 2011). : 72). Language style is a form of rhetoric, namely the use of words in speaking and writing to convince or influence listeners and readers (tarigan, 2005: 5).

E. Emotion Expression

Sarwono (2010) explains that emotion is a positive or negative judgment reaction from a person's nervous system to stimuli from within or from outside a person. Emotions are described in a stimulus both from outside the human object, situation and weather or from within in the form of blood pressure, sleepiness, etc. to the senses and the same feeling. In everyday actions, feelings such as feelings of displeasure, feelings of pleasure are often accompanied in the actions of a person who. the feeling of pleasure and displeasure in everyday life is called the effective or effective color of the tun which is often strong, sometimes weak or sometimes faint. In a strong affective color, the company's feelings will become deeper and more directed so that a mental or psychological level is achieved at the biological or physiological level only (Sarwono, 2010). 2010). Modern psychologists differ in their definition of emotion.

Chaplin (2011) states that an aroused state of the organism in which there are conscious changes, deep nature and behavioral changes. Goleman (2002) defines that emotion is a feeling and thought that is typical of a biological and psychological condition and a tendency to act. Emotions are reactions from outside stimuli and within the individual, for example, happy emotions are a reflection of a person's mood so that his physiological physiology looks laughing, sad emotions encourage crying behavior. Emotions are explained on the basis of physiological events resulting from emotions.

According to Darwin (in Ekman, 2003:14), the expression of human emotions is unique but is found in various living things such as animals, the point of social events experienced by humans will produce the same

emotions as experienced by animals. Darwin (in Ekman, 2003:14), is the result of continuous experiments carried out by referring to his revolutionary theory. As one of the first scientists, Darwin (in Ekman, 2003:14) used the judgment method in studying the conditional value of a strong expression so that it is often discussed with psychological methods.

Hertinjung and Partini, (2010: 5) explain that if emotional expression is high, negative attitude reflection acts as a stressor in determining vulnerability and recurrence in a person's psychological disorder. Meanwhile, Hertinjung and Partini (2010: 5) argue that emotional expression is an index of the overall index of emotions, attitudes and behaviors that are expressed in a community or family. According to Hertinjung and Partini (2010:6), emotional expression is an index of the overall index of emotions, attitudes and behaviors that are expressed in a community or family.

Based on the description of emotional expression, it is explained that emotional expression is an effort for someone in the form of communication of emotional status in an effort to feel status as a response to internal and external situations based on physiological changes and behavioral tendencies according to goals.

F. Language of Women's Emotions

Language is a system of arbitrary sound symbols used by a community in interacting, collaborating and for self-identification (Kridalaksana, 2008:24). Language is a means of communication between community members in the form of sound symbols produced by human speech tools (Keraf, 1997: 1).

Emotional language is a language that is issued as an overflow of emotions in a person. That will be an understanding in the purpose of the language point of language emotion can make people understand something, there is a message that is felt, there is a message that is conveyed and there is a message that will be received. Talking about what is to be conveyed, delivery and how people receive it, emotional language is a form of symbol of resistance from a group which becomes the strength of the structure in demanding a change in emotional language points from an argumentative perspective, which is the use of language in arousing certain emotions for the interlocutor so that it leads to conclusions. certain.

Euphemisms speak to support a judgment. Euphemisms are used to soften harsh realities, function from an argumentative point of view. Euphemisms have appropriate conventional meanings for example, if someone has 'passed away', that he is not dead (Groarke and Tindale, 2004: 187. However, euphemisms are used to describe aspects of reality, the interlocutor The language of emotion is used in two basic modes of words evoke emotions and present a reality that is different from the point of positive or negative states is used to modify the evaluation of a situation that has been known previously. The existence of this difference will understand the relationship between the meaning of words and the resulting emotion (Macagno and Walton, 2012: 165).

Language describes emotion after being consistent with the psychological constructionist theory of emotion. Psychological constructs are theories that understand emotions as the result of psychological "combinations" of more basic combinations of psychological "elements" that are not themselves specific to emotion (Lindquist, 2013). All constructionist theories of emotion predict that psychological compounds such as anger, disgust, fear, arise when more basic psychological elements such as bodily representations, exteroceptive sensations (eg, visual sensations; auditory sensations) and conceptual knowledge of emotional categories are combined.

Jendra (2010) states that Sociolinguistics is a branch of linguistics that takes language as its object of study, in a way that is usually distinguished from the way it is handled in terms of syntax, semantics, morphology, and phonology. Coulmas (in Wardhaugh, 2006) states that micro sociolinguistics investigates how social structure affects the way people speak and how language variations and usage patterns correlate with social attributes such as class, gender, and age.

G. Psycholinguistics

Psycholinguistics etymologically, the term comes from two words, namely psychology and linguistics (Andika and Harras, 2009:1). Psychology is described as the science of human behavior by understanding the nature of the stimulus, the nature of the response, and thought processes before the stimulus or response occurs. Psychology is the science of studying human thought processes and all their manifestations in regulating human behavior. The purpose of the thought process is to understand, explain, and predict human behavior.

Psycholinguistics is a combined approach of psychology and linguistics in the study of language knowledge, in usage, language, and matters related to it, either separately or separately. Psycholinguistics is a discipline that investigates and describes the psychological processes that enable humans to master and use language. Psycholinguists conduct research on speech development and language development and how individuals of all ages understand and produce language. For the description of language, this field relies on the findings of linguistics, namely the discipline that describes the structure of language. Although the acquisition, understanding, and production of language have been at the core of psycholinguistic research, the field has developed rapidly since its inception: The neurology of language function is currently of interest to psycholinguists, especially for those who study sex differences, aphasia, language after congenital or acquired injury. in the immature brain, and impaired language development (dysphasia).

According to Clark and Clark (1977) (in Dardjowidjojo 2005: 7), there are three things related to the psychology of language, namely comprehension, production, and language acquisition. Psycholinguistics is formed from the word psychology and the word linguistics, each of which stands alone with different procedures and methods. But both of them examine language as its formal object. The two objects

will have different materials, linguistics examines the structure of language, while psychology examines language behavior or language processes (Chaer 2003:5).

Psycholinguistics is an integration of two disciplines; psychology and linguistics. Psychology is the study of mind and behavior; linguistics is the study of language. So, in general, psycholinguistics can be interpreted as the study of thought and language. It deals with the relationship between the human mind and language as it studies the processes that occur in the brain when producing and understanding language. Psycholinguistics covers three main points; language production, language perception and language acquisition. Language production refers to the processes involved in creating and expressing meaning through language. Language perception refers to the processes involved in interpreting and understanding spoken and written language. Language acquisition refers to the process of acquiring native or second language speakers.

Psycholinguistics has provided many theories that explain the three points above. These theories are very useful in the field of language teaching. Some experts use it as a basic theory in developing language teaching methods. This is known as the psycholinguistic approach. The psycholinguistic approach views language and thought as related but completely independent phenomena. Learning is seen as an individual cognitive process that occurs within the individual and then moves to the social dimension. Psycholinguistics as a science that studies the psychology of language is manifested in language teaching. It helps to study the psychological factors that may be involved in language learning. Psycholinguistics focuses on the actual application of language and communication.

Psycholinguistics is a psychological decomposition that takes place when someone explains the sentences that are heard when using communication and have language skills by humans (Chaer 2003:5). The main goal of psycholinguistics is a theory of language in which linguistics can be accepted and can explain the nature of language and its acquisition. Psycholinguistics tries to explain the essence of the structure of language if it is used in speaking when understanding the narrative sentence. (Chaer 2003:6). Psycholinguistics concerned with communication focuses on the modification of messages during communication in relation to speech and speech understanding in certain situations.

Linguistics is a science that studies language. Language in the linguistic context is an arbitrary, conventional, sound system used by humans as a means of communication (Andika and Harras, 2009:1). This shows that linguistics does not mean language with phenomena in general. Language is a language that has a distinctive and unique structure. Psycholinguistics is related to the development of linguistic studies. The term psycholinguistics was originally *linguistic psychology* (linguistic psychology) and some call it *psychology of language* (language psychology). The results of collaboration are more focused and systematic, so that later psycholinguistics emerges (psycholinguistics).

Psycholinguistics is a science that describes psychological processes that occur when someone uses understanding sentences when communicating and human language skills are obtained (Andika and Harras, 2009:1). Aitchison (1984) defines psycholinguistics as the study of language and thought. Psycholinguistics is a field of study that links psychology with linguistics. A psycholinguist aims to discover the structures and processes underpinning the human ability to speak and understand language. Psycholinguists are not interested in language interactions among language speakers but in exploring when individuals speak.

III. METHODS

The approach used in this research is qualitative. Moleong (2007:6) defines qualitative research as research that intends to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by research subjects holistically and by way of description in the form of words and language in a special natural context. The data in this study is divided into two types. including primary data and secondary data (Sugiyono, 2017:45) Primary data, namely the data used in this study in the form of direct interviews from participants in the form of language and meaning used by the socialite woman community and secondary data, namely data obtained through other parties interested and related in this research

The method in this study has several stages, including (1) determining the location; (2) participant selection, (3) data collection; (4) data analysis, and (5) presentation of data analysis results. This research was conducted in the city of Jember with several women's socialite communities. The choice of location is because in the City of Jember many socialite communities of mothers and mothers are formed. The research location is at the secretariat of the Mamesh Squad Boutique Shanti Jalan Bedadung No. 41 Jember. The research subjects of this study were female socialite participants who were members of the Mamesh Squad in the city of Jember, which consisted of the head of the Mamesh Squad, members who used SiSeSa. The number of research subjects is 5 people from how many members of the Mamesh Squad are 25 people.

Types of data that used in this study in the form of direct interviews from participants in the form of language and its meaning used by the socialite woman community. Primary data were obtained directly from participants, namely subjects who were involved in physical mental and emotional activities. Primary data is the result of interviews with women from the Mamesh Squad who use SiSeSa. The results of the interviews were processed into words in the form of diction and language style needed in this study.

Secondary data, namely data obtained through other interested parties and related in this research. Secondary data is related to written documents, literature and so on to support emotional expression. Secondary data in the form of documents, articles and journals that support the data in the study. The data can be in the form of SiSeSa profiles, Mamesh Squad and previous research.

The data in this study are in the form of diction (word choice) and language style in expressing emotions as well as the terms used by socialite women in expressing emotions after having SiSeSa branded goods when communicating with fellow community members. The diction used expresses their joy and admiration when they have SiSeSa while the style of language used is the language style used when expressing their emotions when they have SiSeSa robes.

The type of triangulation used in this research is triangulation by method. Qualitative analysis with an approach to the interactive nature of data collection or data collection. The process in this analysis is cyclical, not linear, so that data collection activities cannot be separated from data analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Analysis of Psycholinguistic Studies in the Language of Women's Emotions

Communication with language is done in a variety of situations. In general, language situations are divided into two, namely official and informal situations. The official situation in the classroom is required to use standard language, language that refers to the rules. In informal situations, it is more appropriate to use non-standard language, namely language that prioritizes the main function of language rather than language rules. Non-standard language is used so that the atmosphere is more intimate and more communicative. For this reason, it can use everyday language that does not prioritize language rules.

Emotion is basically a form of communication. When a person is in an emotional state, it means he is trying to convey a message to others. Various forms of delivery, depending on the environment and socio-cultural conditions that shape it. This research is part of Psycholinguistics. The use of language in expressing emotions can be categorized as a new learning. Mastery of language is part of human learning in general, closely related to personality, closely intertwined with culture of second language learning, involves distraction, creation of new linguistic systems, and learning of discourse and communicative functions of language.

The language used by people in emotional situations is informal language. By using informal language, it will feel more familiar and hit the target intended by the speaker to the speaker who wants to have a direct and indirect conversational dialogue. In communicating, each of the above individuals hold the interaction which is manifested in speech acts and gestures. Speech acts in an interaction can sometimes invite anger, stress, fear, discomfort, and anxiety which are manifested in various ways.

The psycholinguistic situation in the expression of emotions in this chapter is studied based on psycholinguistics. Psycholinguistics is a science that studies language and psychology. Psycholinguistics deals with the study of language acquisition and linguistic behavior, especially the psychological mechanisms responsible for these two aspects. The use of language by speakers is not random, but must consider several factors, including who is

speaking, who is the interlocutor, what topic is being discussed and where the speech event occurs.

Emotions after buying SiSeSa branded clothing products are basically an urge to act, an immediate plan to overcome a problem that has been gradually implanted or evaluation and emotions as well as typical feelings and thoughts, a psychological state and a series of tendencies to act. The emotions that arise are joy and admiration. Good communication will make the situation better too, but communication in the form of actions that will harm others from speaker to addresser or makes communication that is not fluent so that conversations in different situations lead to uncontrollable actions of expressing emotions in Indonesian.

The emotional language expressed by women after buying SiSeSa branded products generally expresses the emotions of joy and admiration after buying SiSeSa branded clothing products. Psycholinguistic situations that occur in women who buy SiSeSa branded clothing products generally express emotions of joy and admiration for the SiSeSa brand.

B. Situations Psycholinguistics Emotions Joy of women

Psycholinguistic situations that exist in various forms of different situational contexts with their location, nature and actions that show them express emotional statements to the interlocutor. The emotional statements that are often carried out by the emotions that are analyzed from the socialite Mamesh Squad women as emotional data analysis, are very contrary to the expressions used in spoken and written language. Sometimes in language, the emotion of joy emphasizes verbal and nonverbal language because after buying a product from the SiSeSa brand, it shows emotions that express joy.

Based on this expression, the emotion of joy given by sociality women when buying SiSeSa products. The use of language and the choice of various languages as well as combining them with nonverbal aspects in realizing effective communication. Nonverbal aspects both quantitatively and qualitatively can cause negative psychological responses.

The emotional language aspect of happy people is actually a response or reaction in verbal form from people who are happy. Based on the language we can know people who are happy. The language spoken is usually accompanied by movements of body parts. This can be explained by expressing the emotions of joy from the emotional language expressed by women after buying SiSeSa products.

C. Identify the Emotion Language Diction used Mamesh Squad Socialite Women Have SiSeSa Branded Shirts in Jember City

Socialite Mamesh Squad aims to determine the type of diction used in the emotions of Socialite Mamesh Squad women. This study says that the choice of words or diction, vocabulary in Indonesian can be classified into abstract words, concrete words, general words, special words, popular words, study words, standard words, non-standard words, native words and loan words. The types of diction are in the form of denotative words and connotative words.

The choice of words or diction is the ability to accurately distinguish the nuances of meaning from the idea to be conveyed, and the ability to find a form that is suitable (suitable) with the situation and sense of value possessed by the listener community group. Diction or word choice in language practice is actually a question of The ability of a word can also be a phrase or group of words to generate the right idea in the imagination of the reader or listener (Rahardi, 2009:31).

Diction is the choice of words to express ideas. Good diction relates to the choice of words that are meaningfully appropriate and in harmony, whose use is in accordance with the subject matter, events, and audiences of readers or listeners (Panuti, 2006:21). Diction is the choice of words to express ideas.

Emotions as intense feelings of reaction to something affect a person in interacting with others such as in making choices, actions, and perceptions. Emotional is based on a person's feelings or attitudes in reacting to a condition. Emotional is a distinctive feeling and thought, a biological, psychological state and a set of tendencies to act. Therefore, women in expressing emotions often express in words that describe the feelings they experience.

In expressing women's emotions, the researchers found nine types of relevant diction, which include abstract words, concrete words, common words, special words, popular words, study words, non-standard words, original words, and loan words. In addition, the researchers found two types of diction in the form of denotative words and connotative words in expressing women's emotions. diction or word choice has a broader meaning, not only used to express the words used to express an idea or idea, but also includes the issue of phraseology or how to use words or phrases in a broader construction, both in spoken and written form. , language styles, and expressions. In diction must be able to distinguish denotation and connotation, be able to distinguish synonymous words, distinguish words that are similar in spelling, and knowing loan words from foreign languages. In other words, diction is the use of words by the author to describe an essay. Diction is not just choosing words, but also expressing an idea so that from the choice of words a certain effect is obtained.

In women's emotions, diction is found in the form of abstract words. There are 10 abstract words found. The abstract word in the woman's emotions is in the form of a concept or understanding. This is in line with Soedjito (1988: 39) who explains that abstract words have a reference in the form of a concept or understanding. The abstract word in the woman's emotions has a reference in the form of a concept or understanding that is difficult to describe because it cannot be absorbed by the five human senses. This shows that abstract words are words that have a referent in the form of a concept, abstract words are difficult to describe because the reference cannot be absorbed by the five human senses. The use of abstract words in women's emotions is intended so that the concept or understanding of abstract words that socialite women want to convey hits the reader.

The concrete word is found in the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad women. There are 4 concrete words found. The concrete word in the woman's emotions is in the form of objects that are perceived by the five senses. This is in accordance with Soedjito (1988:39) who said that the concrete word reference is an object that is perceived by the five senses. The word concrete used in women's emotions is intended so that the reference in the form of an object that can be perceived by the senses that the socialite woman wants to convey can be understood by the reader.

In women's emotions when buying SiSeSa, there are types of diction in the form of common words. There are three common words found by researchers. This common word in women's emotions has a wide scope and covers many things. This is in accordance with Soedjito (1988: 41) which states that general words are words that have a broad scope and can cover many things. In addition, the word common in women's emotions also refers to many things, to the group, and to the whole. This is in line with the understanding of the general word is a word that has a broad scope. The word general also refers to many things, to the set, and to the whole. The use of common words in women's emotions is intended to give a broad picture to the reader.

The special word is a type of diction found in the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad women. In the woman's emotions, researchers found 13 special words. The special words found have a narrow and limited scope. In line with this, Soedjito (1988: 41) says that special words are words that are narrow or limited in scope. The word special in female emotion refers to a specific and concrete object. This provides an explanation which states that special words are words that refer to specific and concrete directions. The word special refers to a specific object. The special word used in women's emotions is intended to give a narrow picture to the reader so that the information conveyed can be seen clearly.

In the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad women, a type of diction is found in the form of popular words. There is 1 popular word in the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad woman. The popular word in women's emotions is known and used by all walks of life. In line with this, Soedjito (1988: 43) says that the word popular is a word that is known and used by all levels of society in daily communication. Besides being in accordance with Soedjito's opinion, popular words were found which said that popular words are words that are commonly used by all levels of society, either by the educated or by the common people.

The use of popular words in women's emotions is intended to make it easier for socialite women to understand the content to be conveyed in the woman's emotions. The word study is a type of diction found in the emotions of the socialite Mamesh Squad women. Researchers found 8 study words. The study words found are words that are known and used by educated people in scientific works. The explanation that the scientific word is a word used by educated people, especially in scientific writings. There is a difference in the mention of the type of diction. This type of diction is called the word study, while Keraf calls it a scientific word.

However, the essence of the two statements is actually the same. In women's emotions, The expression of women's emotions is found in the type of diction in the form of non-standard words. In the woman's emotions, the researchers found 4 non-standard words. Non-standard words found in women's emotions are not in accordance with predetermined or customary rules. In line with this, Soedjito (1988: 44) says that non-standard words are words that do not follow the rules or varieties of language that have been determined or customary. The use of non-standard words in women's emotions has the intention of making it more flexible when read by socialite women. The word non-standard gives a familiar impression to the socialite woman who reads it.

The original word is a type of diction found in the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad women. Researchers found 22 original words. The original word found in female emotions is of English origin. The original word that was found came from the original language, namely English. The use of English words in women's emotions gives an attractive impression of the services or products offered.

In women's emotions, diction is found in the form of absorption words. In the woman's emotions, the researchers found 15 loan words. The loan words found in women's emotions come from foreign languages. In line with this, Soedjito (1988: 47) says that loanwords are words that originate (absorb) from regional or foreign languages. In women's emotions, loan words are used to give the impression of luxury and to describe the products or services offered.

In addition, there are types of diction in the form of denotative words. There are 2 denotative words found in this study. Denotation words found in women's emotions are in the form of meanings that are easy to understand because they are real meanings. It is appropriate to say that the denotative meaning is the real meaning. Words that contain denotative meanings are easy to understand because they do not contain ambiguous meanings, although they are still general in nature. This general meaning means the meaning that is clearly known by everyone. The denotation words found are straightforward and objective. This is in line with the opinion of Kridalaksana (2009: 46) which says that the denotative meaning is the meaning of a word based on a straightforward designation and the meaning contained is objective.

The word connotation is a type of diction found in the emotions of the socialite Mamesh Squad women. There are 7 connotation words found. The connotation words found contain emotional values and cause feelings of agreement or disagreement with women's emotions. It was explained that the connotation meaning is a stimulus and response meaning that contains emotional values. Part of the connotative meaning arises because of the opposite feeling (agree or disagree). In line with this opinion, Tarigan (2015: 50) says that connotation is an emotional response that is individual. The use of the word connotation is intended to bring up a stimulus and response to the reader so that the reader has emotional values when reading the woman's emotions.

The original word diction is the most commonly found in the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad women. The original word found in the woman's emotions was in English. By using native words (English), it is hoped that women's emotions can influence socialite women more than using Indonesian.

D. Identify the Emotion Language Style Used Mamesh Squad Socialite Women Owns SiSeSa Branded Shirts in Jember City.

Women are creatures who are able to express emotions when there are events or events that they experience. Ekman stated that there are six basic emotions based on his observations through facial expressions—and these are universal—that is, happiness, surprise, fear, sadness, anger, and disgust (Ekman, 1992). The basic emotions based on language data are anger, sadness, fear, joy, and love. Cabanac (2002) who divides the types of emotions into two valences—pleasant and unpleasant, then happy and love include pleasant emotions, while anger, sadness, and fear are unpleasant emotions.

Expression of women's emotions is often expressed in various styles of language. Language style and emotion are closely related to each other. The relationship can be seen from someone describing or expressing a woman's emotions through stylistic features. Humans can experience certain facial expressions intentionally, but generally facial expressions are experienced accidentally as a result of these human feelings or emotions. It's usually very difficult to hide certain feelings or emotions from the face, although many people feel very anxious to do so. For example, a person who tries to hide his feelings of hatred towards someone, at some point will accidentally show his feelings on his face, even though he tries to show a neutral expression. The relationship between feelings and facial expressions can also work the other way around.

The function of language style in communication is as a tool to: (1) increase taste, which means it can increase the interest of the reader or listener to follow what the writer or speaker says, (2) influence or convince the reader or listener, meaning that it can make the reader or listener more confident. and steady towards what the author or speaker conveys, (3) creates a certain mood, meaning that it can bring the reader into a certain mood, such as good or bad impressions, feelings of pleasure or displeasure, hatred, and so on after capturing what is stated. the author, and (4) strengthen the effect on the idea, which can impress the reader with the ideas conveyed by the author in his work.

The analysis of language style in the emotions of Mamesh Squad socialite women aims to determine the type of language style used in the emotions of Mamesh Squad socialite women after buying the SiSeSa robe. This study refers to the type of language style according to Tarigan (2013: 4-5). Tarigan (2013: 4-5) divides the types of language style into four groups, namely comparative language style, contradictory language style, linking language style, and repetition language style.

Findings on the expression of women's emotions Socialite Mamesh Squad, researchers found four types of language styles that are relevant to Tarigan's theory (2013: 4-5). These language styles include hyperbole, alliteration, personification, and metaphor. The expression of the socialite Mamesh Squad woman's emotions was found in the type of language style in the form of hyperbole. There are 23 types of hyperbole styles found. The hyperbole found in women's emotions is an exaggeration. This is in accordance with the opinion of Tarigan (2013: 55) who says hyperbole is a type of language style that contains statements that are exaggerated in number, size or nature with the intention of emphasizing a statement or situation to intensify, enhance its impression and influence. In line with this, Hyperbole is a kind of figurative language that contains an exaggerated statement, by exaggerating something. The use of hyperbole is expected to increase the impression and influence of women's emotions on socialite women who read it.

Alliteration is a type of language style found in the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad women. The researcher found three alliterations in the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad women. In the woman's emotions, the alliteration found uses the repetition of words that start with the same sound. In line with this, Tarigan (2013: 175) states that alliteration is a type of language style that uses *purwakanti* or the use of words that start with the same sound. In addition, alliteration is a kind of language style in the form of repetition of the same consonants. Alliteration becomes decoration and emphasizes what is to be conveyed in women's emotions to socialite women who read women's emotions.

In addition, in expressing women's emotions, a type of language style is found in the form of personification. There are three personifications found. In the woman's emotions, the personification found is the attachment of human traits to inanimate objects. This is in accordance with the opinion of Tarigan (2013: 17) who says that personification is a type of language style that attaches human traits to inanimate objects and abstract ideas. Personification is a figurative language that describes inanimate objects or inanimate objects as if they have human characteristics. The use of personification is expected to be able to express the feelings of women after buying SiSeSa.

Metaphor is a type of language style found in the emotions of the socialite Mamesh Squad women. The researcher found three metaphors in the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad women. The metaphor found in women's emotions is a brief comparison of two ideas. This is in accordance with the opinion of Tarigan (2013: 14) who says that metaphor is a kind of comparative language style that is the shortest, densest, and neatly arranged. It contains two ideas: one is a fact, something thought, which becomes an object; and the other is a comparison to the reality earlier. Based on this, it can be explained that metaphor is a kind of analogy that compares two things directly.

Hyperbole is the language style that is most prominent or dominant in its use in the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad women. The hyperbole contained in the woman's emotions aims to increase her impression and influence on the reader because hyperbole itself is a style of language that exaggerates something that will easily affect the reader.

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be seen that the diction used in the emotions of the socialite Mamesh Squad women varies in number. Although it varies, from the ten types of word classification, nine types of word classification were found because one type of diction, namely the standard type of words was not found in the woman's emotions. Likewise, the types of diction in denotative and connotative words. Researchers found nine types of denotative and connotative words.

The use of the type of language style in women's emotions Socialite Mamesh Squad used is a supporter of a woman's emotion. The use of language style provides beauty in a woman's emotions. In women's emotions, the style of language used includes 23 types of hyperbole, three types of alliteration, three types of personification, and three types of metaphor. Overall there are 32 uses of language styles used in women's emotions.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the discussion, the researcher can draw the following conclusions. First, the emotional language diction spoken by the socialite Mamesh Squad woman in expressing her feelings when she owned SiSeSa branded clothes in Jember City was found to include abstract words, concrete words, general words, special words, popular words, study words, non-standard words, native words, and loan words as well as denotative and connotative words. The type of word diction that is not found in expressing women's emotions is standard words. The number of dictions found varies. The researcher found ten abstract words, four concrete words, three general words, 14 special words, one popular word, eight study words, four non-standard words, 22 original words, and 15 borrowed words, as well as two denotative words and seven connotative words.

Second, emotional language style used Mamesh Squad socialite women in expressing their feelings when they have SiSeSa branded clothes in Jember City consist of four types of language styles contained in the emotions of Mamesh Squad Socialite women. The four types of language style are metaphorical language style, alliteration language style, personification style, and metaphor language style. Hyperbole is the most widely used type of language style. The researcher found 23 hyperbole language styles, three alliteration styles, three personification styles, and three metaphorical styles. Hyperbole is the language style that is most prominent or dominant in its use in the emotions of the Socialite Mamesh Squad women.

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